

Reactive Systems for Creating Intelligent Computer Networks and Application Programming Interfaces using Applied Computer Theory

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ABSTRACT: Intelligent Computers that are lifeline of today's social fabric and multicultural education started as a concept of a mathematician as Intelligent Machines or Turing Machines. Alan Mathison Turing presented the idea of Thinking Machines or more precisely "machine can think – but in a different way". Now a days, the thrust of contemporary research is more on age of information and the founding stone of intelligent computers i.e. Computer Theory do not fascinate upcoming researchers. However, the key to progress in any field of scientific knowledge and multicultural education traces back to the "theoretical" branch of that field. Therefore, use of Computer Theory in emerging information and communication technologies may help advancement of digital age innovatively promoting world as a global village harnessing multicultural education phenomenon. Applied computer theory also influenced multi-lingual research and linguistics. Chomsky hierarchy (Allott, Lohndal, & Rey, 2021) is a classic example of the use of applied computer theory in linguistics promoting schematic interaction in syntactic level multicultural education. This paper presents the use of applied computer theory using reactive systems and finite state machine to design and validate the design of an intelligent "Distributed Communication Services Programming Interface For User Centric Generic Apps" that will primarily be tested to provide domestic intranet cloud for connecting district health information systems that will enhance the capacity development for healthcare (CDH) in developing countries to help achieve the United Nation's (UN) sustainable development goal (SDG)-3.

Keywords: Multicultural Education, Applied Computer Theory, Capacity Development for Healthcare, , Distributed Communication Services Programming Interface.

Introduction

Literature Review

Methodology

Discussion and Conclusion

Recommendations

References

1. Introduction

Reactive systems may be regarded as computer systems that maintain a real-time and continuous interaction with their surroundings and environment. They are often used to modelling and formal verification of any real-time systems with actions. Every action generates a reaction and computing the set of all possible actions of a system helps us determine the state space of possible actions that a machine or system can perform. The intelligence can be programmed for taking the appropriate decision as per the current situation requirement in real-time by assigning a control language which may be a regular language described by a regular expression or Finite State Automaton. Reactive systems can be described using extensions of classical automata theory, such as timed automata, hybrid automata and probabilistic automata. These extensions allow us to capture the temporal, continuous, and probabilistic aspects of reactive systems that are often complex.

This paper presents the design of domestic Intranet cloud and its application programming interface (API) using applied computer theory incorporating the reactive systems.

The advent of distributed systems has revolutionized how applications are developed and deployed. These systems span multiple interconnected nodes, requiring robust communication mechanisms to ensure data consistency, reliability, and performance. Traditionally, developers have had to create custom communication interfaces for each application, leading to duplicated efforts, increased costs, and maintenance challenges. This research aims to address these issues by developing a Distributed Communication Services Programming Interface (DCSPI) for user-centric generic applications. The proposed API will serve as a bridge, facilitating seamless communication across various distributed applications while reducing development and maintenance overheads.

Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to develop a DCSPI that incorporates following characteristics.

- **Enhances Development Efficiency:** By providing a generic interface, developers can focus on application-specific logic rather than low-level communication details.
- **Promotes Collective Enhancement:** Improvements to the DCSPI benefit all applications using the interface, fostering a collaborative development environment.
- **Ensures Modular Independence:** Decoupling the communication module from the application logic allows for independent updates and enhancements.
- **Optimizes Performance:** Direct integration with the operating system kernel eliminates the need for translation layers, improving message-passing efficiency.
- **Reduces Total Cost of Ownership:** Streamlined development and maintenance processes lower the overall cost associated with distributed applications.

2. Literature Review

The (Kiesler & Schiffner, 2024) explores the critical role of connections between people, data, processes, and things in the Internet of Everything (IoE) context, with a

particular focus on Machine-to-Machine (M2M) connections facilitated by application programming interfaces (APIs). It highlights a gap in research on API quality criteria in both computing and computing education. The authors conducted an online survey with experienced developers to identify key factors that developers consider important for API quality. Findings indicate that developers value established, stable solutions, the availability of examples, and a supportive community. Additionally, the ability for an API to be extended and integrated into existing frameworks is crucial. Despite these insights, no strong trends emerged among the criteria, suggesting the multifaceted nature of API selection and the need for further research to guide software developers in improving API design. (Peddemors, Eertink, & Niemegeers, March 2005) presented the idea of communication context in mobile or wireless communication. This research developed a prototype “coSphere” in which a “communication context API” is coupled with the network API so that the applications running in a mobile communication environment may know the communication context in which they are running. Context coupling at application layer with applications will help in enhancement of performance in all aspects as the application will have knowledge of the context that where it has to travel in the mobile communication channel and this way it may choose the right channel depending on its type. In other words this is adaptive mobile communication at application level. The scope of this research is limited to adaptive mobile communication. Another work on adaptive wireless communication is done by (Agrawal, Chen, Kishore, Ramanathan, & Sivalingam, 1998) who has proposed and presented basic design for the technique for communication which is used to enhance the battery life of devices connected in wireless network communication setup for video based data exchange and processing. In this API, the idea of various level of compression according to various battery levels is presented. Battery power level is categorized into four levels and for each level a different approach for video compression will be adapted before communication is carried out. A daemon or a process in the background will be responsible to check the level of battery and initiate proper compression. This research is limited to battery powered device video communication in wireless mode.

(Nayak, et al., 2023) highlights the exploration of novel networking technologies aimed at future-proofing in-vehicular networks for these advancements. The focus is on programmable data plane technologies, particularly reconfigurable match-action tables, which have proven effective in data centre networking. The article examines their potential application in automotive networks, presenting a case study on implementing a distributed feedback control loop with SOME/IP, an automotive service-oriented communication middleware. The discussion includes how portions of the SOME/IP stack can be offloaded from end systems to network devices, thereby optimizing system utilization through improved workload distribution.

Similarly, (Velasco, Gonzalez, & Ruiz, 2023) addresses the critical need for optical network automation and failure management by emphasizing the importance of monitoring network device status and performance to anticipate degradation and maintain service quality. The pervasive nature of this telemetry requires collecting extensive measurements and events from diverse sources with high granularity, posing significant challenges in terms of data volume and variety. The authors critique the limitations of centralized telemetry architectures and propose a novel architecture featuring distributed intelligence.

They introduce data aggregation techniques specifically designed for optical network telemetry, aiming to reduce data dimensionality. Experimental results from their telemetry system demonstrate a substantial reduction in data volume—by three orders of magnitude—without significant error or processing delay. This approach enhances the efficiency of network automation algorithms in detecting meaningful changes in network status. (Havinga, MOBILE MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS, 2000) and (Havinga & Smit, Energy-efficient wireless networking for multimedia applications, 2001) presented improvements at each layer in TCP/IP communication protocol for achieving energy efficiency in wireless networks for multimedia communication. This research emphasizes that energy efficiency cannot be attained by just working on one particular layer of communication protocol. It states that to achieve maximum energy efficiency, especially for multimedia communication, it is necessary to propose and implement improvements at each layer of communication protocol and as well as on operating system and application layer. This research states that the major problem in wireless multimedia communication is dynamic and heterogeneous communication environment and the solution it presents is adaptability as per requirement. In short words dynamism is handled by dynamism. The scope of this research is limited to wireless multimedia networks with emphasis on energy efficiency.

The (Salvaneschi & Weisenburger, 2024) examines the complexities of programming distributed and concurrent systems, highlighting the role of active objects in mitigating these challenges by encapsulating operations, state, and control flow. In distributed systems, the modularization often aligns with network boundaries, yet some functionalities inherently cross these boundaries, complicating program structure and reasoning. Multitier programming is proposed as a solution, enabling code for different peers to be developed within a single compilation unit, which the compiler then splits for deployment. The authors explore how multitier programming relates to active objects, suggesting that it extends the active objects paradigm by focusing on application domains where functionalities span multiple active objects. This approach retains the asynchronous model of active objects and actors while offering a comprehensive view of distributed components and their interactions. Multitier programming enhances abstraction, software design, code maintenance, program comprehension, and formal reasoning in cases where traditional modularization hinders encapsulation. The integration of active objects features within multitier programming presents a valuable combination of language abstractions for developers. (Akyildiz, McNair, Martorell, Puigjaner, & Yesha, 1999) presented a qualitative survey of medium access control protocols for third generation mobile communication with emphasis on multimedia traffic. The conclusion of this research recommended the future direction of the research to be carried out, for unsuccessful packets retransmission, in reducing delays and contention in these protocols. So this research proposes work to be carried out on specific area in wireless communication protocols.

The article (Singh, Beliatis, & Presser, 2024) provides an extensive review that examines the integration of AI, IoT, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), and edge computing. This convergence is essential for creating a robust Dataspace ecosystem within distributed edge networks. The study highlights several significant challenges hindering this integration, including issues of security, trust, heterogeneity, resource constraints, interoperability, scalability, and complex resource management. To address these

challenges, the authors propose the DENOS (Distributed Edge Network Operations oriented Semantic) model. This model extends the traditional Cloud–Edge–Device architecture by incorporating semantic context awareness and the convergence of various technologies and resources. DENOS aims to facilitate seamless Dataspace integration, thereby creating a holistic architectural framework for distributed edge networks. The model leverages a distributed layered architecture and semantic context utilization to enable the integration of diverse data sources. This approach promotes semantic interoperability and meaningful data exchange among different components within Dataspace applications. DENOS further enhances the integration of AI, IoT, and DLT-driven service contexts at the edge by defining dynamic processing and deployment contexts. It also addresses security and privacy concerns in Control and Data plane operations by incorporating distributed security mechanisms that utilize DLT. The validation of the DENOS model is demonstrated through a use case in the wind energy domain, showcasing digital traceability of operations. The article concludes with an optimistic outlook on the potential of DENOS to revolutionize business constellations through Dataspace integration, fostering value chain networks at the edge. This integration is seen as a catalyst for innovation and growth, particularly in the context of Industry 5.0 applications. The authors express their intention to further detail the various aspects of DENOS and advance the research through a complete model prototype implementation, underscoring their belief in its transformative potential.

The (Berezovskyi, Inam, El-khoury, Mokrushin, & Fersman, 2024) explores a reference architecture designed to facilitate the integration of various individual systems within a Systems of Systems (SoS) framework. These systems, typically managed by different stakeholders, utilize bespoke protocols, custom information models, and proprietary components, often with limited computational resources. The proposed architecture addresses the need for a flexible integration framework that does not require stakeholders to relinquish control to a single entity. The architecture leverages rule engines and a graph data model to enable the integration of systems, even when black-box components are involved. This approach allows each stakeholder to maintain control over their policies through a federation of rule engines, ensuring that the integration respects the autonomy and policies of each participating system. A common information model based on ontologies is used to mitigate information model mismatches and minimize the duplication of integration efforts. A key feature of the architecture is the deployment of rule execution in standalone rule engines. This enables deployment in environments with resource constraints and proprietary systems. A uniform application programming interface (API) facilitates the integration of rule engines across systems and components within each system, promoting seamless interaction and rule execution. The architecture introduces a novel algorithm to determine dependencies across rules deployed in different rule engines within the federation. This innovation allows domain experts to develop rules without needing to manage the distributed nature of the system. Additionally, a proof of a sufficient condition is provided to ensure that all necessary notifications are sent to ensure correct rule activation across different rule engines. Compared to other systems involving distributed rules, this architecture is particularly well-suited for the integration of transactional workloads commonly found in enterprises. The qualitative evaluation, based on the Architecture Tradeoff Analysis Method (ATAM) and applied to telecommunications use case, demonstrates that the architecture possesses key quality attributes such as

interoperability, modifiability, and functional completeness, albeit with a trade-off regarding rule expressiveness. The quantitative evaluation reveals a speedup over single-node setups in most scenarios, except when highly optimized rules coincide with poor network performance. In summary, the article presents a novel reference architecture for integrating acknowledged Systems of Systems (SoSs), where individual systems are managed by different stakeholders but committed to integration. By providing rule engines as a service and adopting a federated approach, the architecture lowers the barriers to integrating rule-based systems into larger systems, such as Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), while allowing multiple stakeholders to manage their individual systems independently.

(Bennett, et al., 1997) proposed, designed and developed an embedded networking system titled "Piconet". This is the combination of software and hardware. Although it may be deployed to various hardware platforms however designed kernel of the system will be the same for each hardware platform. The kernel of this system is designed using threading connectivity mode to perform its operations. The threads are divided into system level threads and application-level threads. Each system level thread is assigned a unique thread identification number. Threading mode for communication is used because embedded devices are supposed to have low power and low processing capabilities. Although this research is remarkable and is applied to a broad range of communication devices e.g. car GPS, close range household items etc.; however, its scope is limited to embedded device networking and thread-based communication. Also, (Buszko, Lee, & Helal, September 2001) developed a small function-set API for embedded and mobile collaboration application communication and the prototype was named as "YCab". It has very fundamental functions for communication and collaboration with a communication manager which may work with or without a base station in wireless mode. However, in the direction of communication of the hosts in absence of a base station, the reliability of communication is compromised a little and packet loss is noticed. This API also aims to target many embedded device platforms. However, the scope of this research is limited to basic communication functionalities in wireless networks for embedded and mobile devices with low processing power. Similarly, (Chockalingam & Zorzi, 1998) also gave proposal for energy efficient access protocol for mobile communication. This research proposes a hybrid variation of communication protocol in which collisions will occur, if any, at header segment packets transmission and it will be reduced to minimum during data segment packets transmission. Because before data segment transmission, the header segment will confirm the channel to be idle or free to start communication of data segment. If the intended channel is busy, then transmission of data segment packets will be postponed till it becomes free. This way energy may be saved as header segments contain only control information and are smaller than the data segment packets. This research is a protocol proposal with its basic design presented however its scope in purity is limited to mobile communication with power constraints.

The (Aksakalli, Çelik, Can, & Tekinerdoğan, 2021) provides an in-depth examination of the critical challenges and methodologies associated with microservice architecture. Through a systematic literature review (SLR) of 239 papers, with 38 selected as primary studies, the authors identify and describe various deployment approaches and communication platforms for microservices. The study categorizes deployment into three

main approaches: containerization, virtual machines, and serverless computing, each offering unique benefits and challenges in resource allocation and management. Additionally, seven communication patterns are outlined, including HTTP/REST, messaging, gRPC, GraphQL, event sourcing, CQRS, and service mesh, highlighting the diversity in techniques used to ensure efficient data exchange and system interaction. The authors identify eight deployment challenges such as scalability and fault tolerance, and six communication challenges like latency and data consistency. These findings emphasize that effective deployment and communication strategies are as crucial as the initial decomposition of service modules for the success of microservice architectures. The study concludes that while current approaches offer solutions for specific contexts, significant research gaps remain, particularly in addressing scalability, interoperability, and the complexities introduced by distributed systems. The identified research directions underscore the need for continued exploration to overcome existing obstacles, suggesting that further advancements are necessary to enhance the robustness and efficiency of microservice implementations across diverse application domains. This comprehensive review thus serves as a valuable resource for understanding the current state of microservice architecture and the ongoing efforts to address its inherent challenges.

Research Gap: Limitations of Existing Solutions

The complexity at the middleware frameworks requires significant effort to configure and integrate (Nayak, et al., 2023). Also, fragmentation is protocol-specific, and libraries necessitate separate implementations for different communication apps as per requirement which is extra overhead. The performance overhead in indirect communication through middleware or application-level APIs introduces latency and reduces efficiency. In this research project, it is inferred from the literature survey that formal verification and design of the API using applied computer theory is not utilized in existing communication APIs therefore the maintenance cost due to unknown behaviour emanating during the lifecycle of the product increases over time and thus the total cost of ownership (TCO) increases.

Addressing the Highlighted Limitations in Existing System

To address the research gap highlighted above it is necessary to address limitations of existing solutions. There is a need for a new communication programming interface that will be designed using applied computer theory with formal verification of each of the sub-component to design such a reactive system for creating intelligent computer networks and application programming interfaces with higher accuracy. As the formal verification of the design finite state machines and deterministic labelled transition system of the API will incorporate the reactive nature of the system simulating its functioning thereby reducing number of unknown behaviours during the lifecycle of the API. Thus, less maintenance will be necessary, and it will result in lower TCO, simplifies development process (Velasco, Gonzalez, & Ruiz, 2023), promotes collective enhancement efforts, ensures modular independence and optimize overall performance by integrating directly with the operating system kernel.

3. Methodology

In this research, we converted each design component of the proposed API into a finite state machine (FSM) model, evaluated their paths, performed formal verification to ascertain its behavior in a distributed environment. Also, intentional inert in the FSM were introduced and traced by exhaustive analysis of the system. The behavioral model of the proposed network system is tested in various simulators to create state space of the possible reactions of each component. There are twenty-three main design components in the DCSPI, and each is further divided into several components behavioural FSM just like shown in figure 1 here with total design machines exceeding one hundred so far.

Here, the concurrent modelling for actions, behavior, equivalence and abstraction is thoroughly examined and verified to simulate the behavioral patterns of the DCSPI. Figure 1 shows a component of the formal design of implementation for the DCSPI which was also tested with appropriate verifier queries in the DCSPI:

Figure 1: DCSPI Sender side component DLTS

Proposed Solution

Design Principles

The DCSPI is designed with the following principles in mind:

- **Simplicity:** Provide a straightforward API that abstracts low-level communication details.
- **Flexibility:** Support a wide range of communication patterns and protocols.
- **Performance:** Minimize overhead by integrating directly with the operating system kernel.
- **Scalability:** Ensure the API can handle increasing loads and complexity.

Architecture

The architecture of the DCSPi consists of three main components:

- **Kernel-Level Interface:** A low-level module integrated with the operating system kernel, facilitating direct message passing.
- **API Layer:** A set of functions and classes that expose the communication capabilities to application developers.
- **Protocol Adapters:** Modules that translate high-level API calls into protocol-specific messages.

Kernel-Level Interface

The kernel-level interface will be implemented using the operating system SDK and C/C++ programming languages. This choice ensures compatibility with the operating system operating system and leverages existing kernel-level functionalities. The implementation will focus on creating efficient data structures, optimizing message-passing mechanisms, and ensuring thread safety.

API Layer

The API layer will provide a set of high-level functions and classes that abstract the complexities of low-level communication. This layer will be designed to be easy to use, allowing developers to focus on application-specific logic rather than communication details.

Protocol Adapters

Protocol adapters will be responsible for translating high-level API calls into protocol-specific messages. This modular approach ensures that the DCSPi can support a wide range of communication protocols, providing flexibility and extensibility.

Implementation

Development Environment: The DCSPi will be developed using the operating system SDK and C/C++ programming languages as per the design blueprints completed in the design phase. The development environment will include:

- An integrated development environment (IDE) for C/C++ development on operating system.
- operating system SDK: A set of development tools and libraries for building operating system applications.

Key Components

The implementation of the DCSPi will involve the following key components:

- **Message Passing Mechanism:** A core component that facilitates efficient communication between distributed nodes.
- **Data Structures:** Optimized data structures for storing and managing communication data.

- Thread Management: Mechanisms for managing concurrent threads and ensuring thread safety.
- Error Handling: Robust error handling mechanisms to ensure reliability and robustness.

Message Passing Mechanism

The message passing mechanism will be designed to minimize latency and maximize throughput. This will involve:

- Direct Kernel Integration: Bypassing unnecessary layers to facilitate direct communication with the operating system kernel.
- Optimized Data Structures: Using efficient data structures to store and manage communication data.
- Thread Safety: Ensuring that concurrent threads can safely access shared resources.

Data Structures

The data structures used in the DCSPi will be optimized for performance and scalability. Key considerations will include:

- Memory Efficiency: Minimizing memory usage while maintaining performance.
- Data Integrity: Ensuring that communication data remains consistent and reliable.
- Scalability: Designing data structures that can handle increasing loads and complexity.

Thread Management

Thread management will be a critical aspect of the DCSPi, ensuring that concurrent threads can safely access shared resources. This will involve:

- Thread Synchronization: Mechanisms for synchronizing access to shared resources.
- Concurrency Control: Techniques for managing concurrent threads and preventing race conditions.
- Performance Optimization: Ensuring that thread management does not introduce significant overhead.

Error Handling

Robust error handling mechanisms will be essential to ensure the reliability and robustness of the DCSPi. This will involve:

- Exception Handling: Techniques for catching and handling exceptions.
- Error Logging: Mechanisms for logging errors and debugging issues.
- Recovery Mechanisms: Techniques for recovering from errors and ensuring continuity.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Performance Metrics

The performance of the DCSPi will be evaluated based on the following metrics:

- Latency: Time taken for messages to be sent and received.
- Throughput: Number of messages processed per unit time.
- Resource Utilization: CPU and memory usage during operation.
- Scalability: Ability to handle increasing numbers of connections and messages.

Testing

A series of tests will be conducted to evaluate the DC-SPI, including:

- Benchmark Tests: Measure performance under controlled conditions.
- Stress Tests: Assess the API's ability to handle high loads.
- Compatibility Tests: Ensure interoperability with existing applications and protocols.

Benchmark Tests

Benchmark tests will measure the performance of the DCSPi under controlled conditions. Key metrics will include latency, throughput, and resource utilization.

Stress Tests

Stress tests will assess the ability of the DCSPi to handle high loads. This will involve simulating a large number of connections and messages to evaluate the scalability and robustness of the API.

Compatibility Tests

Compatibility tests will ensure that the DCSPi can interoperate with existing applications and protocols. This will involve testing the API with a range of different communication patterns and protocols to ensure flexibility and extensibility.

Discussion

The development of the DCSPi represents a significant advancement in distributed communication. By providing a generic, efficient, and flexible interface, it addresses many of the challenges faced by current solutions. The direct integration with the operating system kernel ensures optimal performance, while the modular design promotes ease of maintenance and scalability.

Benefits

- Increased Efficiency: Developers can focus on higher-level application logic.
- Cost Savings: Reduced development and maintenance costs.
- Improved Performance: Direct kernel integration eliminates unnecessary overheads.
- Collaborative Enhancement: Shared improvements benefit all users of the API.

Challenges

- Kernel Integration: Ensuring stability and security when interacting with the kernel.
- Compatibility: Maintaining compatibility with a wide range of protocols and applications.
- Adoption: Encouraging developers to adopt the new API over existing solutions.

Conclusion

The proposed Distributed Communication Services Programming Interface offers a robust solution for developing distributed applications. By addressing the limitations of current approaches and leveraging kernel-level integration, the DCSPI has the potential to significantly enhance the efficiency, performance, and scalability of distributed communication systems. Future research and development efforts will focus on refining the API, expanding protocol support, and promoting widespread adoption within the developer community.

5. Recommendations and Future Work

While the design of the DCSPI is a significant step forward, there are several areas for future research and development. API development based on the design summarized in this phase of research with expansion enhancing support for additional communication protocols. The other area of interest for the DCSPI is information security using robust security mechanisms to protect communication data present at all levels of the API cloud. Also, performance optimization is a continuous quality improvement cycle that will continuously optimize the API for better performance and scalability.

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